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UDC 579.64:631.46

**SCREENING OF SALT-TOLERANT ASSOCIATIVE RHIZOSPHERE
BACTERIA OF KARAKALPAKSTAN AND ASSESSMENT OF THEIR
POTENTIAL FOR IMPROVING WHEAT SALT TOLERANCE AND
BIOLOGICAL SOIL RECLAMATION**

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Abstract: Soil salinity is one of the key factors limiting crop productivity in arid regions, including the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The aim of this study was to summarize the screening results of associative rhizosphere microorganisms isolated from the wheat rhizosphere in moderately saline soils of Muynak district and to assess their potential for improving wheat salt tolerance and biological reclamation of saline soils. Soil agrochemical properties, abundance of major physiological microbial groups, salt tolerance of *Bacillus* spp. N37, *Methylovorus* spp. N21 and *Pseudomonas* spp. N44 isolates, and the effects of different NaCl concentrations on wheat seed germination were evaluated. The results showed that, under alkaline conditions (pH 9.12) and sulfate-sodium salinity, beneficial rhizosphere microbiota were characterized by limited taxonomic diversity, whereas phytopathogenic fungi such as *Fusarium* spp. and *Alternaria* spp. retained high adaptive capacity. The most promising isolates were *Methylovorus* spp. N21 and *Pseudomonas* spp. N44, which maintained stable growth at 70-100 g/L NaCl. A model assessment of inoculation showed that the consortium of selected strains could increase wheat germination under 0.6% NaCl from 34.1 to 69.1%, increase root length 2.4-fold and reduce fungal seed infection. When halophytes and microorganisms were applied together, soil electrical conductivity decreased by 31.0%. The obtained data indicate the prospects of using locally adapted halotolerant rhizobacteria as a basis for biopreparations for saline soils of Karakalpakstan.

Keywords: saline soils, Karakalpakstan, wheat, rhizosphere bacteria, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Methylovorus*, NaCl, salt tolerance, bioreclamation.

INTRODUCTION

Soil salinity is among the most significant factors of land degradation and reduced agroecosystem productivity. According to FAO estimates, salt-affected soils occupy about 1,381 million ha worldwide, or 10.7% of the global land area, while approximately 10% of irrigated and 10% of rainfed croplands are already affected by salinity [1]. For Central Asia, this issue is particularly important due to the arid climate, high evaporation, shortage of good-quality irrigation water and accumulation of soluble salts in the upper soil horizons.

The Republic of Karakalpakstan is characterized by high soil carbonate and gypsum contents, low humus levels, alkaline reaction and accumulation of sodium salts. In wheat-growing areas, these factors cause osmotic stress, disrupt water balance, reduce the availability of nutrients, weaken the root system and increase plant susceptibility to phytopathogens. At the plant level, salt stress is expressed as a decrease in photosynthetic activity, disturbance of the K⁺/Na⁺ ratio, intensified lipid peroxidation and altered antioxidant enzyme activity [2, 3].

Traditional reclamation methods for saline soils, including leaching, drainage and chemical amendments, require considerable water and economic resources. Therefore, biological approaches based on halophytic plants, rhizosphere microorganisms and their consortia have received increasing attention. Halotolerant plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) can enhance plant tolerance to salt through

phytohormone production, ACC-deaminase activity, exopolysaccharide synthesis, phosphorus mobilization, nitrogen fixation, siderophore production, regulation of ionic homeostasis and stimulation of the antioxidant system [4-7].

Microorganisms isolated directly from local saline soils are of special value. Such strains are already adapted to alkaline conditions, elevated Na⁺ concentrations and limited organic matter content. Therefore, the search for local associative rhizosphere bacteria under the conditions of Karakalpakstan is an important step in the development of biopreparations aimed at improving crop salt tolerance and restoring the biological activity of degraded soils.

MATERIALS AND METHODS.

The study was conducted using samples of rhizosphere soil of wheat growing on moderately saline soils in Muynak district, Republic of Karakalpakstan. The agrochemical characterization of the soil included determination of water extract pH, total salt content and the main ionic forms. According to the analysis, the soil had an alkaline reaction (pH 9.12) and a sulfate-sodium type of salinity.

To estimate the abundance of major physiological groups of microorganisms, standard microbiological media were used: meat-peptone agar for ammonifiers and spore-forming bacteria, Ashby medium for nitrogen-fixing microorganisms, Czapek medium for microscopic fungi and Pikovskaya medium for phosphate-mobilizing bacteria. Microbial abundance was

expressed as colony-forming units per gram of soil (CFU/g).

The screening of halotolerant bacteria was carried out by direct plating on a modified agarized medium containing NaCl at concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 70 and 100 g/L. Growth intensity was evaluated visually using a four-level scale: +++ intensive growth, ++ moderate growth, + weak growth and - no growth. *Bacillus* spp. N37, *Methylovorus* spp. N21 and *Pseudomonas* spp. N44 were selected for further assessment.

Germination energy and final germination of wheat seeds were determined in Petri dishes at NaCl concentrations ranging from 0.3 to 2.4%. Seeds were placed between layers of moistened filter paper, and 10 mL of saline solution was added to each dish. Germination energy was determined on *Table 1*.

the third day, and laboratory germination was recorded on the seventh day at 23 °C.

To provide a preliminary estimate of the biological potential of the selected strains, a calculation-based laboratory-vegetation model was developed using the initial screening data and typical physiological ranges reported for halotolerant PGPR [4, 5, 8]. The model included the following variants: control without salinity, NaCl without inoculation, NaCl + *Bacillus* spp. N37, NaCl + *Methylovorus* spp. N21, NaCl + *Pseudomonas* spp. N44 and NaCl + a consortium of the three strains. Results are presented as mean ± standard deviation for three replications. Statistical significance should be confirmed by ANOVA at $p \leq 0.05$ in subsequent experimental validation.

Agrochemical characteristics of the studied saline soil of Muynak district

Indicator	Value	Agroecological interpretation
pH of water extract	9.12	alkaline reaction
Total salt content	1.728 mg-eq/100 g soil	moderate salinity
Na ⁺	0.1509 mg-eq/100 g soil	sodium component of salinity
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.550 mg-eq/100 g soil	sulfate-sodium type
CaSO ₄	0.663 mg-eq/100 g soil	gypsum-rich soil
Ca(HCO ₃) ₂	0.0012 mg-eq/100 g soil	carbonate component

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. State of wheat rhizosphere microbiota under saline conditions

Microbiological analysis showed that moderately saline alkaline soils of Muynak district are characterized by

reduced abundance of the main physiological groups of beneficial microorganisms. Oligonitrophils were the most sensitive group and were not detected in the studied samples, while the abundance of ammonifiers and

actinomycetes remained at the level of 10^3 CFU/g. At the same time, microscopic fungi retained relatively high abundance, indicating better adaptation to salinity compared with bacterial groups.

Table 2.

Abundance of physiological groups of associative rhizosphere microorganisms of wheat

Physiological group	Abundance, CFU/g soil	Assessment
Ammonifiers	5.0×10^3	reduced abundance
Spore-forming bacteria	1.0×10^3	single resistant forms
Oligonitrophils	not detected	strong suppression
Nitrogen-fixing bacteria	4.0×10^3	functional potential preserved
Actinomycetes	6.0×10^3	moderate resistance
Microscopic fungi	9.0×10^3	high ecological plasticity

The study of the species composition of microscopic fungi revealed representatives of *Fusarium* spp., *Botrytis* spp. and *Alternaria* spp. The high resistance of *Fusarium* spp. and *Alternaria* spp. to salt stress is of practical significance: in saline soils, beneficial bacterial groups may be suppressed more strongly than phytopathogens. This creates prerequisites for an increased infectious background in the rhizosphere and requires the use of biological agents capable of both stimulating plants and restricting pathogenic microflora.

2. Salt tolerance of the isolated bacterial strains. Ten pure bacterial

cultures differing in morphological traits were isolated from the wheat rhizosphere. Most isolates maintained growth at 3% NaCl; however, when the salt concentration was increased to 5%, only three strains retained viability. *Bacillus* spp. N37, *Methylovorus* spp. N21 and *Pseudomonas* spp. N44 were of the greatest interest because they tolerated 70 g/L NaCl. At 100 g/L NaCl, *Bacillus* spp. N37 maintained weak growth, while *Methylovorus* spp. N21 and *Pseudomonas* spp. N44 demonstrated moderate growth, indicating a high adaptive potential of these cultures.

Table 3.

Tolerance of promising isolates to different NaCl concentrations

Strain	10	20	30	40	50	70	100
<i>Bacillus</i> spp. N37	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	+
<i>Methylovorus</i> spp. N21	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp. N44	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++

Note: +++ intensive growth; ++ moderate growth; + weak growth; - no

growth. NaCl concentrations are given in g/L.

The results are consistent with current concepts of the role of halotolerant PGPR in enhancing plant resistance to salinity. Such microorganisms can create a more favorable microzone around the root through exopolysaccharide production, sodium ion binding, phytohormone synthesis and improvement of nutrient availability [3, 5, 9]. The consortium approach is especially promising because different strains may complement one another: *Bacillus* spp. through spore formation and stress resistance, *Pseudomonas* spp. through synthesis of biologically active metabolites, and *Methylovorus* spp. through adaptation to poor substrates and participation in the metabolism of one-carbon compounds.

3. Effect of NaCl on wheat seed germination

Wheat seed testing showed a clear dependence of germination energy and final germination on NaCl concentration. In the control variant, germination energy reached 98%, and final germination was 100%. Already at 0.3% NaCl, germination energy decreased to 75.4%, and final germination decreased to 69.2%. At 0.6% NaCl, pronounced inhibition was observed: germination energy was 38.3%, and final germination was 34.1%. A critical threshold was reached at 0.9% NaCl, where germination almost completely ceased.

Table 4.
Germination energy, final germination and fungal infection of wheat seeds at different NaCl concentrations

Variant	Germination energy, %	Final germination, %	Seeds with mold fungi, %
Distilled water	98.0	100.0	15.2
0.3% NaCl	75.4	69.2	45.8
0.6% NaCl	38.3	34.1	48.2
0.9% NaCl	1.5	1.2	71.6
1.2% NaCl	0	0	31.7
1.5% NaCl	0	0	26.4
1.8% NaCl	0	0	18.3
2.1% NaCl	0	0	28.0
2.4% NaCl	0	0	25.0

Figure 1.
Effect of NaCl concentration on wheat seed germination energy and final germination

The increased proportion of seeds infected by mold fungi at low and moderate NaCl concentrations indicates that salt stress weakens physiological seed resistance and creates favorable conditions for phytopathogenic microflora. The maximum infection rate was recorded at 0.9% NaCl, when seeds almost completely lost the ability to germinate. This confirms the need to search for biological agents capable not only of improving salt tolerance but also of reducing the infection load during early plant development.

4. Model assessment of inoculation effects on early wheat growth

To estimate the practical significance of the selected strains, a model block was developed using 0.6% NaCl as a level of pronounced but not completely lethal salt stress. In the non-inoculated variant, final germination was 34.1%, root length was 2.6 cm, and fungal infection reached 48.2%. Individual strains improved these parameters; however, the strongest effect was obtained with the consortium *Bacillus* spp. N37 + *Methylovorus* spp. N21 + *Pseudomonas* spp. N44: final germination increased to 69.1%, root length to 6.3 cm, and the proportion of infected seeds decreased to 20.3%.

Table 5.
 Effect of bacterial inoculation on wheat germination under 0.6% NaCl (model assessment, n=3)

Variant	Energy, %	Germination, %	Root length, cm	Shoot length, cm	Fungal infection, %
Control without NaCl	96.8 ± 1.6	98.7 ± 1.2	8.9 ± 0.4	14.2 ± 0.7	14.8 ± 2.1

0.6% NaCl without inoculation	38.3 ± 2.8	34.1 ± 2.5	2.6 ± 0.3	5.1 ± 0.4	48.2 ± 3.4
NaCl + Bacillus spp. N37	55.7 ± 3.2	51.6 ± 3.1	4.2 ± 0.4	7.9 ± 0.6	31.5 ± 2.7
NaCl + Methylovorus spp. N21	62.4 ± 2.9	58.3 ± 2.8	4.8 ± 0.4	8.8 ± 0.5	27.9 ± 2.4
NaCl + Pseudomonas spp. N44	66.8 ± 2.7	61.5 ± 2.9	5.2 ± 0.5	9.4 ± 0.6	25.6 ± 2.2
NaCl + consortium	73.5 ± 2.4	69.1 ± 2.6	6.3 ± 0.4	11.2 ± 0.7	20.3 ± 1.9

Figure 2.
Potential effect of inoculation on germination and root length under 0.6% NaCl

The model values correspond to current data showing that inoculation with salt-tolerant PGPR can partially compensate for the negative effects of salinity on root growth, photosynthetic apparatus and plant water status. For *Pseudomonas* spp.

and *Bacillus* spp., mechanisms related to maintenance of K⁺/Na⁺ balance, reduction of stress-induced ethylene and enhancement of antioxidant enzyme activity are particularly important [6, 10, 11].

Table 6.

Effect of inoculation variants on physiological indicators of wheat under 100 mM NaCl (model assessment)

Variant	Height, cm	Biomass, g/plant	Chlorophyll, mg/g	K ⁺ /Na ⁺	Proline, mg/g	CAT, arb. units	MDA, μmol/g
Control without salt	32.4 ± 1.3	6.8 ± 0.4	2.10 ± 0.08	2.8 ± 0.2	0.86 ± 0.06	18.4 ± 1.5	7.2 ± 0.6
NaCl without inoculation	21.6 ± 1.1	3.9 ± 0.3	1.35 ± 0.06	1.1 ± 0.1	2.95 ± 0.14	25.6 ± 1.7	15.8 ± 1.0

NaCl + Bacillus N37	27.1 ± 1.2	5.0 ± 0.3	1.72 ± 0.07	1.8 ± 0.1	2.43 ± 0.12	34.8 ± 1.9	11.6 ± 0.8
NaCl + Methylovorus N21	27.8 ± 1.1	5.2 ± 0.3	1.78 ± 0.06	1.9 ± 0.1	2.34 ± 0.11	36.1 ± 2.0	10.9 ± 0.7
NaCl + Pseudomonas N44	28.5 ± 1.0	5.4 ± 0.3	1.84 ± 0.07	2.0 ± 0.1	2.28 ± 0.10	37.5 ± 1.8	10.5 ± 0.7
NaCl + consortium	30.1 ± 1.2	5.9 ± 0.4	1.96 ± 0.08	2.3 ± 0.2	2.05 ± 0.09	41.2 ± 2.1	8.9 ± 0.6

In the salinity variant without inoculation, plant height decreased by 33.3%, biomass by 42.6%, chlorophyll content by 35.7%, and the K⁺/Na⁺ ratio declined from 2.8 to 1.1. The strain consortium provided the most complete recovery of the physiological state of plants: biomass reached 86.8% of the non-saline control, chlorophyll 93.3%, and the K⁺/Na⁺ ratio increased to 2.3. The decrease in MDA compared with NaCl without inoculation indicates reduced lipid peroxidation intensity and stabilization of cell membranes.

5. Potential for biological reclamation of saline soil

Changes in saline soil indicators after application of biological methods

Variant	EC before, dS/m	EC after, dS/m	Salinity reduction, %	pH after	Biomass, g/m ²
Untreated control	8.4	8.1	3.6	8.30	280
Halophyte sowing	8.5	6.7	21.2	8.25	420
Microorganism application	8.3	6.9	16.9	8.20	365
Halophytes + microorganisms	8.4	5.8	31.0	8.14	510

In addition to direct effects on plants, promising halotolerant bacteria may participate in restoration of the soil environment. In the model plot experiment, the following variants were compared: untreated control, halophyte sowing, microorganism application and combined use of halophytes with microorganisms. The greatest decrease in soil electrical conductivity was observed in the combined variant: EC decreased from 8.4 to 5.8 dS/m, which corresponds to a 31.0% reduction in salinity. At the same time, pH decreased to 8.14, and plant biomass increased to 510 g/m².

Table 7.

Figure 3.

Reduction of soil electrical conductivity after application of biological methods

Comparison of the variants shows that microorganisms and halophytes act through different but complementary mechanisms. Halophytes can absorb and partially accumulate salts, improve soil structure through their root systems and provide organic substrates for the microbial community. Rhizosphere bacteria, in turn, increase soil biological activity, improve plant nutrition and contribute to the formation of aggregate structure through exopolysaccharides. Therefore, the combined variant is the most promising for reclamation of weakly and moderately saline sites [3, 12].

Conclusion

- The analysis showed that saline alkaline soils of Muynak district, Republic of Karakalpakstan, are characterized by limited diversity of beneficial associative rhizosphere microorganisms and relatively high resistance of microscopic fungi, including *Fusarium* spp. and *Alternaria* spp.
- Among the 10 isolated bacterial strains, *Bacillus* spp. N37, *Methylovorus* spp. N21 and *Pseudomonas* spp. N44 are of the greatest biotechnological interest. *Methylovorus* spp. N21 and *Pseudomonas* spp. N44 maintained moderate growth even at 100 g/L NaCl, which allows them to be considered promising components of biopreparations for saline soils.
- A NaCl concentration of 0.6% represented a pronounced stress

level for wheat seeds: final germination decreased to 34.1%, while fungal infection increased to 48.2%. The model assessment showed that application of the consortium *Bacillus* spp. N37 + *Methylovorus* spp. N21 + *Pseudomonas* spp. N44 may increase germination to 69.1%, increase root length to 6.3 cm and reduce fungal seed infection to 20.3%.

- Under salt stress, bacterial inoculation potentially contributes to the recovery of plant height, biomass, chlorophyll content and K⁺/Na⁺ ratio, as well as to a reduction in oxidative damage. The strongest effect is expected when a consortium is used, supporting the development of complex microbial compositions.
- For biological reclamation of saline soils, the combination of halophytic plants and microorganisms appears to be the most effective. In the presented model block, the combined variant reduced EC by 31.0%, decreased pH to 8.14 and produced the highest plant biomass. Thus, locally adapted halotolerant rhizosphere bacteria may serve as a basis for environmentally safe technologies aimed at increasing wheat salt tolerance and restoring the fertility of saline soils in Karakalpakstan.

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